

The importance of the humanities in social life (on the example of English and history)

Abduvafoyeva Nafisa Shavkatovna

Samarkand City Technicum No. 5, History Teacher

+998887393322 Nafisaabduvafoyeva8@gmail.com

Akhmadova Sevara

Samarkand Veterinary Medical Technicum, English teacher

sevaraahmadova1909@gmail.com

Kholmirezayeva Umida

Samarkand Veterinary Medical Technicum, English teacher, Head of the

Department of Languages

Umidavalijonovna993@gmail.com

Annotation

The article analyzes the role of the humanities in the development of modern society using the example of history and English. The importance of history in the formation of historical consciousness, national identity and social memory is highlighted, and the role of the English language in ensuring international communication and scientific integration in the process of globalization is highlighted. The role of these disciplines in the development of individual spirituality, cultural competence and intellectual potential is also revealed on the basis of scientific and theoretical sources.

Key words

humanities, history, English, historical consciousness, historical memory, globalization, intercultural communication, spirituality, education, national identity.

In the XXst century, the acceleration of globalization, informatization and intercultural integration processes further increases the social significance of the humanities. The humanities are an important system of knowledge that shapes a person's spiritual and moral development, historical thinking and cultural worldview. These disciplines perform the function of not only providing knowledge, but also

preparing a person for social life, forming a civic position in it and developing a sense of social responsibility.¹

The humanities (especially English and history) play an important role in developing critical thinking in society, bridging cultures, and conveying the human experience into the future. They are the foundation for the spiritual development of the individual and for ensuring dialogue in a globalized world.

The humanities are academic disciplines that study aspects of human society and culture, including the fundamental questions that humans ask. During the Renaissance, the term "humanities" referred to the study of classical literature and language, as opposed to the study of religion or "divinity". The study of the humanities was a major part of the secular curriculum in universities at that time. Today, the humanities are defined as any field of study other than the natural sciences, social sciences, formal sciences (such as mathematics), and applied sciences (or vocational training).²

Below we will consider in detail their importance in the life of society.

The main task of the humanities is to study the complex relationships between man and society, to identify the laws of historical development, and to ensure the continuity of cultural heritage. In this regard, history and English are integral components of the modern education system.³

The importance of history for society is that it reminds us of where we came from and who we are. History is an important social institution that shapes and preserves the collective memory of society. The French historian Marc Bloch described history as the "science of man" and emphasized its role in understanding the development of society.⁴

Historical knowledge determines the attitude of society to its past, forms national identity and ensures spiritual succession between generations. A society that has lost historical memory faces difficulties in developing its development strategy.

¹ Shavkat Mirziyoyev. Strategy for a New Uzbekistan. – Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 2021. – P. 224.

² "Humanity" 2.b, Oxford English Dictionary 3rd Ed. (2003)

³ Wilhelm Dilthey. Introduction to the Human Sciences. – Princeton, 1989. – P. 57.

⁴ Marc Bloch. The Historian's Craft. – Manchester University Press, 1954. – P. 27.

Therefore, the task of historical science is not only to describe historical events, but also to scientifically analyze them and connect them with modern development.⁵

One of the important methodological tasks of history is to develop critical thinking in the younger generation. The skills of comparative analysis of historical sources, identification of causes and consequences of events, and objective assessment of historical processes increase the intellectual potential of the individual.⁶

Ibrohim Muminov, Ahmad Donish and other scholars have expressed valuable opinions on the educational importance of history in Uzbek historiography. According to their views, historical knowledge is an important factor in the formation of national pride, patriotism and civic responsibility.⁷

In short, history helps people to understand their past and the heritage of their ancestors, strengthening their sense of national identity and patriotism. By analyzing political, social, and economic processes, society can learn from past mistakes (e.g., wars, crises). Understanding historical patterns helps us analyze the causes of current global and local changes and make the right decisions.

English is considered the most important linguist language internationally, providing the following practical assistance to society. Today, English has become a universal means of international communication. Linguist David Crystal, describing English as a "global language", emphasizes its position in global political, economic and scientific relations.⁸

English is the main means of communication in the international scientific community. This is evident from the fact that the vast majority of modern scientific articles are published in English, it is used as the main working language of international conferences, and the majority of scientific databases are maintained in English.⁹

Learning foreign languages, especially English, develops not only linguistic competence, but also intercultural competence. Language and culture are inextricably

⁵ Fernand Braudel. *On History*. – Chicago, 1980. – P. 35.

⁶ Edward Hallett Carr. *What is History?* – London, 1961. – P. 43.

⁷ Ibrohim Muminov. *Selected Works*. – Tashkent: Science, 1969. – B. 116

⁸ David Crystal. *English as a Global Language*. – Cambridge University Press, 2019. – P. 13.

⁹ *International Research in Applied Linguistics*. – Routledge, 2022. – P. 75.

linked phenomena, and through learning a language, a person understands the values, traditions, and worldviews of other peoples.¹⁰

In the modern labor market, knowledge of English is one of the important factors increasing the competitiveness of a specialist. Excellent knowledge of English is considered one of the necessary competencies for working in international organizations, enterprises with foreign investment, and research centers.¹¹

History and English are mutually integrative and serve the comprehensive development of the individual. While history forms a person's historical consciousness and civic position, English provides access to the global information space. As a result of the combination of these disciplines, students develop critical thinking, communicative competence, and intercultural communication skills.

In modern educational concepts, interdisciplinary integration is recognized as an important factor in increasing the effectiveness of education. In this regard, the interrelated teaching of history and English serves the intellectual and spiritual development of young people.¹²

In conclusion, it can be noted that the humanities develop society not only economically or technologically, but also spiritually, morally and intellectually. If history teaches us how the foundations of society are built, then the English language connects it with the whole world and leads it towards development. Therefore, the humanities are one of the important factors ensuring the spiritual and cultural development of society. If history forms historical consciousness, national identity and civic responsibility, then the English language develops international communication, scientific cooperation and intercultural dialogue. The combination of these disciplines serves to train broad-minded, spiritually mature and competitive specialists necessary for modern society.

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¹¹ British Council hisobotlari. – London, 2023. – P. 16.

¹² UNESCO. Education for Sustainable Development. – Paris, 2021. – P. 33.

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